

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

A REVIEW ON AMINOGLYCOSIDE ANTIBIOTICS

Mr. Visal C.S *, Dr. Prasobh G.R., Mrs. Sheeja Rekha A.G, Mr. Nishad V.M
Sree Krishna College of Pharmacy and Research Centre, Parassala,
Thiruvananthapuram Dist, Kerala

Article Received: September 2020 **Accepted:** September 2020 **Published:** October 2020**Abstract:**

Aminoglycosides are natural or semisynthetic antibiotics derived from actinomycetes. They were among the first antibiotics to be introduced for routine clinical use and several examples have been approved for use in humans. They found widespread use as first-line agents in the early days of antimicrobial chemotherapy, but were eventually replaced in the 1980s with cephalosporins, carbapenems, and fluoroquinolones. Aminoglycosides synergize with a variety of other antibacterial classes, which, in combination with the continued increase in the rise of multidrug-resistant bacteria and the potential to improve the safety and efficacy of the class through optimized dosing regimens, has led to a renewed interest in these broad-spectrum and rapidly bactericidal antibacterials.

Keywords- Mechanisms of aminoglycoside resistance

Corresponding author:

Mr. Visal C.S *,
Assistant Professor,
Sree Krishna College of Pharmacy and Research Centre,
Parassala, Trivandram Kerala, India 695502
Email: cvisual5@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Visal C.S et al, *A Review On Aminoglycoside Antibiotics.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(10).

INTRODUCTION:

Aminoglycosides are potent, broad-spectrum antibiotics that act through inhibition of protein synthesis. The class has been a cornerstone of antibacterial chemotherapy since streptomycin was first isolated from *Streptomyces griseus* and introduced into clinical use in 1944. Several other members of the class were introduced over the intervening years including neomycin (1949, *S. fradiae*), kanamycin (1957, *S. kanamyceticus*), gentamicin (1963, *Micromonospora purpurea*), netilmicin (1967, derived from sisomicin), tobramycin (1967, *S. tenebrarius*), and amikacin (1972, derived from kanamycin). A shift away from systemic use of the class began in the 1980s with the availability of the third generation cephalosporins, carbapenems, and fluoroquinolones, which were perceived to be less toxic and/or provide broader coverage than the aminoglycosides. However, increasing resistance to these classes of drugs, combined with more extensive knowledge of the basis of aminoglycoside resistance, has led to renewed interest in the legacy aminoglycosides and the development of novel aminoglycosides such as arbekacin and plazomicin. These latter agents were designed to overcome common aminoglycoside resistance mechanisms thereby maintaining potency against multidrug-resistant (MDR) pathogens.¹

Spectrum of activity

Aminoglycosides are active against various Gram-positive and Gram-negative organisms. Aminoglycosides are particularly potent against members of the Enterobacteriaceae family, including *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *K. oxytoca*, *Enterobacter cloacae* and *E. aerogenes*, *Providencia* spp., *Proteus* spp., *Morganella* spp., and *Serratia* spp. Furthermore, aminoglycosides are active against *Yersinia pestis* and *Francisella tularensis*, the causative agents of plague and tularemia, respectively. The class also has good activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, including methicillin-resistant and vancomycin-intermediate and -resistant isolates, *P. aeruginosa* and to a lesser extent *Acinetobacter baumannii*. Many *Mycobacterium* spp. are also susceptible to aminoglycosides including *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, *M. fortuitum*, *M. chelonae*, and *M. avium*.

Active electron transport is required for aminoglycoside uptake into cells, so the class inherently lacks activity against anaerobic bacteria. Aminoglycosides are also inactive against most *Burkholderia* spp. and *Stenotrophomonas* spp. as well as *Streptococcus* spp. and *Enterococcus* spp. Contemporary large-scale surveillance programs provide an understanding of current

aminoglycoside susceptibility among important pathogens associated with common infection types. A recent surveillance study of Gram negative organisms isolated from patients hospitalized in intensive care units (ICUs) in the United States and the EU found that amikacin and gentamicin showed good activity against key Gram-negative pathogens. In the United States, 99.5% and 87.9% of *E. coli* isolates were susceptible to amikacin and gentamicin, respectively, according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) criteria. Likewise, 97.3% and 87.2% of *E. coli* isolates from the EU were susceptible to amikacin and gentamicin, respectively, according to the European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) criteria.

Among *Klebsiella* spp., 94.8% and 92.7% of U.S. isolates and 90.5% and 83.3% of EU isolates were susceptible to amikacin and gentamicin, respectively. Amikacin was one of the few agents that retained activity against *P. aeruginosa* (97.3% susceptibility in the United States and 84.9% in the EU according to CLSI and EUCAST criteria, respectively). Similarly, aminoglycoside susceptibility rates were high among isolates collected from U.S. medical centers in 2012. In this study, CLSI-based susceptibility rates were 99.0%, 88.2%, and 86.3% among *E. coli* and 88.2%, 89.2%, and 82.4% against *K. pneumoniae* for amikacin, gentamicin, and tobramycin, respectively. However, activity was reduced among *K. pneumoniae* carbapenemase (KPC)-producing *K. pneumoniae*, which are often resistant to multiple classes of drugs, for amikacin (42.5% susceptible), gentamicin (50.0% susceptible), and tobramycin (25.0% susceptible). Amikacin was the most active agent tested against *P. aeruginosa* (98% susceptible), followed closely by tobramycin (90% susceptible) and gentamicin (88.0% susceptible). Broad potency was also observed against *S. aureus* (96.0%, 95.0%, and 76.0% for amikacin, gentamicin, and tobramycin, respectively), but these compounds were less active against *A. baumannii* (58.0% susceptible). The broad-spectrum activity of aminoglycosides is enhanced in vitro through synergy with other classes of antimicrobials. This phenomenon, in which the combined effect of two antimicrobial agents is greater than the sum of their individual effects, is particularly well characterized between aminoglycosides and cell-wall-active agents such as β -lactams. In vitro synergy between aminoglycosides and β -lactams has been observed in both Gram-negative and -positive organisms, including wild-type and MDR isolates, using a variety of methodologies. These in vitro observations have helped to stimulate the use of aminoglycoside-containing combination therapy in the treatment of a number of infection types.

Mechanism of action

Aminoglycosides inhibit protein synthesis by binding, with high affinity, to the A-site on the 16S ribosomal RNA of the 30S ribosome. Although aminoglycoside class members have a different specificity for different regions on the A-site, all alter its conformation. As a result of this interaction, the antibiotic promotes mistranslation by inducing codon misreading on delivery of the aminoacyl transfer RNA. This results in error prone protein synthesis, allowing for incorrect amino acids to assemble into a polypeptide that is subsequently released to cause damage to the cell membrane and elsewhere. Some aminoglycosides can also impact protein synthesis by blocking elongation or by directly inhibiting . The exact mechanism of binding and the subsequent downstream effects varies by chemical structure, but all aminoglycosides are rapidly bactericidal and typically produce a prolonged postantibiotic effect (PAE). The PAE has been shown to be directly related to the length of time that the bacteria take to recover from the inhibition of protein synthesis. It is hypothesized that this is dependent on the eventual disassociation of the antibiotic from its target and exit from the cell. Aminoglycosides are characterized by a core structure of amino sugars connected via glycosidic linkages to a dibasic aminocyclitol, which is most commonly 2-deoxystreptamine.

Aminoglycosides are broadly classified into four subclasses based on the identity of the aminocyclitol moiety:

- (1) no deoxystreptamine (e.g., streptomycin, which has a streptidine ring);
- (2) a mono-substituted deoxystreptamine ring (e.g., apramycin);

- (3) a 4,5-di-substituted deoxystreptamine ring (e.g., neomycin, ribostamycin); or
- (4) a 4,6-di-substituted deoxystreptamine ring (e.g., gentamicin, amikacin, tobramycin, and plazomicin)

The core structure is decorated with a variety of amino and hydroxyl substitutions that have a direct influence on the mechanisms of action and susceptibility to various aminoglycoside-modifying enzymes (AMEs) associated with each of the aminoglycosides. Aminoglycoside entry into bacterial cells is comprised of three distinct stages, the first of which increases permeability of the bacterial membrane, whereas the second and third are energy-dependent. The first stage involves electrostatic binding of the polycationic aminoglycoside to the negatively charged components of the bacterial membrane, such as the phospholipids^{3,4} and teichoic acids of Gram-positive organisms and the phospholipids and lipopolysaccharide (LPS) of Gram-negative organisms, followed by displacement of magnesium ions. These cations are responsible for cross bridging and stabilization of the lipid components of the bacterial membrane and their removal leads to disruption of the outer membrane, enhanced permeability, and initiation of aminoglycoside. This phenomenon facilitates entry into the cytoplasm via a slow, energy-dependent, electron-transport-mediated process. Inhibition of protein synthesis and mistranslation of proteins occurs once aminoglycoside molecules access the cytoplasm. These mistranslated proteins insert into and cause damage to the cytoplasmic membrane itself and facilitate subsequent aminoglycoside entry. This then leads to rapid uptake of additional aminoglycoside molecules into the cytoplasm, increased inhibition of protein synthesis, mistranslation, and accelerated cell death.⁵

Mechanisms of aminoglycoside resistance

Aminoglycoside resistance takes many different forms including enzymatic modification, target site modification via an enzyme or chromosomal mutation, and efflux. Each of these mechanisms has varying effects on different members of the class and often multiple mechanisms are involved in any given resistant isolate. Resistance to aminoglycosides via target site mutations has not been observed because nearly all prokaryotes, with the exception of *Mycobacterium* spp and *Borrelia* spp., encode multiple copies of rRNA. Although contemporary large-scale surveillance programs provide an understanding of phenotypic aminoglycoside resistance among important pathogens, these studies have generally not focused on the epidemiology of specific resistance mechanisms.

Enzymatic Drug Modification

AMEs are often found on plasmids containing multiple resistance elements, including other AMEs or β -lactamases. The mobility of these enzymes might be tied to their origins, which has been hypothesized to be via horizontal gene transfer from the actinomycetes responsible for the natural production of aminoglycosides.

More than 100 AMEs have been described and are broadly categorized into three groups based on their ability to acetylate, phosphorylate, or adenylate amino or hydroxyl groups found at various positions around the aminoglycoside core scaffold. These modifications decrease the binding affinity of the drug for its target and lead to a loss in antibacterial potency. These three families of

AMEs include aminoglycoside N-acetyltransferases (abbreviated AACs), aminoglycoside O-nucleotidyltransferases (ANTs), and aminoglycoside O-phosphotransferases (APHs). The classes are further divided into subtypes according to the position on the aminoglycoside that the enzyme modifies followed by a Roman numeral and, in some cases, a letter when multiple enzymes exist that modify the same position.

Aminoglycoside Acetyltransferases

The aminoglycoside acetyltransferases or AACs comprise the largest group of AMEs. They are part of the GCN5-related N-acetyltransferase (GNAT) superfamily of 10,000 described proteins. These enzymes acetylate amino groups found at various positions on the aminoglycoside scaffold in an acetyl-CoA-dependent reaction. There are four main subclasses of this group of enzymes whose nomenclature is derived from the specific amino group that is modified. Specifically, AAC(1) and AAC(3) target the amino groups found at position 1 and 3, respectively, of the 2-deoxystreptamine ring, whereas AAC(20) and AAC(60) target amino groups found at the 20 and 60 position of the 2,6-dideoxy-2,6-diaminoglucose ring.⁶

Aminoglycoside Phosphotransferases

The second largest group of AMEs is the APHs. This structurally diverse group of enzymes acts like kinases in that they catalyze the ATP-dependent phosphorylation of hydroxyl groups found on aminoglycosides. APH enzymes are functionally and structurally similar to the serine–threonine and tyrosine kinases found in eukaryotes. The modifications made by these enzymes lower binding affinity to the target by decreasing the hydrogen bonding potential of aminoglycoside hydroxyl groups with important rRNA residues. Most of the 30 described APH enzymes belong to the APH(30) subfamily, although variants that target the 200 hydroxyl also exist. These enzymes are found in diverse groups of Gram-negative bacteria, although APH(30)-IIIa was discovered in *S. aureus* and *Enterococcus* spp. All members of the family lead to kanamycin and neomycin resistance with various members of the family also able to modify a variety of other aminoglycosides, including amikacin and gentamicin B.⁷

Aminoglycoside Nucleotidyltransferases

The final group of AMEs is the ANTs. These enzymes act by adding AMP from an ATP donor to hydroxyl groups at the 200, 300, 40, 6, and 9 positions. The most clinically relevant members of the class include ANT(200) and ANT(40), which were first described in *K. pneumoniae* and *S. aureus*, respectively. ANT(200) broadly affects the activity of 4,6-di-substituted aminoglycosides, whereas ANT(40) targets kanamycin A, B, and C,

gentamicin A, amikacin, tobramycin, and neomycin B and C. Other members of this class include ANT(300), ANT(6), and ANT(9), which confer resistance to streptomycin and spectinomycin.

16S rRNA Methylation

Target site modification leading to aminoglycoside resistance occurs via the action of 16S rRNA methyltransferases (RMTs). These enzymes modify specific rRNA nucleotide residues in a manner that blocks aminoglycosides from effectively binding to their target. There are two general classes of RMTs that are characterized by the specific nucleotide residues that they modify. These include enzymes that render bacteria resistant to 4,6-di-substituted aminoglycosides via methylation of the N7 position of nucleotide G1405 and those that affect both 4,6- and 4,5-di-substituted aminoglycosides through methylation of the N1 position of nucleotide A1408.

The first clinical case of a pathogen with an RMT as a mechanism of aminoglycoside resistance was reported in a *P. aeruginosa* isolate from Japan in 2003. This isolate contained a plasmid-encoded RMT, named RmtA for ribosomal methyltransferase A. Subsequently, several additional plasmidborne RMTs, encoded by the genes *armA*, *rmtB1*, *rmtB2*, *rmtC*, *rmtD*, *rmtD2*, *rmtE*, *rmtF*, *rmtG*, and *rmtH*, have emerged in clinical isolates that show high-level resistance to multiple aminoglycosides. These enzymes modify the G1405 nucleotide and, thus, impact the activity of all 4,6-di-substituted aminoglycosides (i.e., amikacin, gentamicin, and tobramycin). In 2007, the enzyme NpmA was discovered encoded on a plasmid in an aminoglycoside-resistant *E. coli* clinical isolate, also from Japan. This methyltransferase modifies the A1408 nucleotide and, thus, impacts 4,6- and 4,5-di-substituted as well as monosubstituted aminoglycosides, conferring pan-aminoglycoside resistance. To date, there has been only one additional report of this enzyme in a clinical isolate.⁸

Efflux-Mediated Resistance

Several members of the resistance–nodulation–division (RND) family of efflux systems have been shown to be involved in intrinsic aminoglycoside resistance in various pathogens. In the opportunistic pathogen *P. aeruginosa*, intrinsic low-level resistance to aminoglycosides, tetracycline and erythromycin, is mediated by the expression of the multiple efflux (Mex) XY-OprM system. MexXY orthologs are found in other species of bacteria. For example, members of the *Burkholderia cenocepacia* complex are often intrinsically resistant to aminoglycosides via RND efflux pumps. A homologous transporter in *E. coli*, AcrD, participates in efflux of aminoglycosides as

does the Acinetobacter drug efflux (Ade) ABC efflux system in *A. baumannii* and the major facilitator superfamily (MFS) in *Mycobacteria* spp.

Molecular Epidemiology of Aminoglycoside Resistance Mechanisms

Comprehensive molecular data regarding the current prevalence of specific aminoglycoside resistance mechanisms among common pathogens is sparse. One recent study evaluated the aminoglycoside resistance mechanisms found among 200 Gram-negative bacilli isolates selected at random from an extensive culture collection (Castanheira et al. 2015). Ninety-nine Enterobacteriaceae (91.9% AME-positive), 49 *A. baumannii* (79.6% AME-positive), and 52 *P. aeruginosa* (63.5% AME positive) with a variety of aminoglycoside resistance profiles were included. A diversity of AME genes were identified with the most prevalent being *aac(60)-Ib* (n ¼ 75), *ant(30)-Ia* (n ¼ 51), and *aac(3)-IIa* (n ¼ 45), and with 26 isolates harboring more than one AME gene. In addition, 21 of the isolates were found to carry an RMT including 12 Enterobacteriaceae, seven *A. baumannii*, and two *P. aeruginosa*. Many of these isolates were also resistant to other common antibiotics used to treat Gram-negative infections, highlighting the ability of these resistance mechanisms to spread through conjugation of plasmids and nonreplicative transposons among bacteria. AMEs are commonly found in association with other key resistance elements, such as carbapenemases and extended spectrum β -lactamases (ESBLs). Among 50 carbapenem-resistant *K. pneumoniae* clinical isolates from two U.S. medical centers (80% possessing KPC-2, 10% possessing KPC-3 with all KPC β isolates also expressing TEM-1 and SHV-12), 98% of isolates expressed at least one AME. Specifically, 98% were positive for *aac(60)-Ib*, 56% positive for *aph(30)-Ia*, 38% positive for *aac(30)-IV*, and 2% positive for *ant(200)-Ia*. Overall, 40%, 98%, and 16% of the strains were nonsusceptible to gentamicin, tobramycin, and amikacin, respectively. Plazomicin, a novel aminoglycoside in clinical development that was designed to evade AME-based resistance, had MICs that ranged from 0.25 to 1 mg/mL against this set of isolates.

AME characterization in 330 aminoglycoside-resistant clinical Enterobacteriaceae isolates from Spain revealed the presence of *aph(300)-Ib* and *ant(300)-Ia* genes in 65.4% and 37.5% of the isolates, consistent with 92% phenotypic resistance to streptomycin found in this strain collection (Miro' et al. 2013). These isolates were resistant to other aminoglycosides to varying degrees, including gentamicin (18.4%), tobramycin (16.9%), and amikacin (1.5%), indicating the presence of other AMEs; *aph(30)-Ia* was found in 13.9% of

isolates, *aac(3)-IIa* in 12.4%, *aac(60)-Ib* in 4.2%, *ant(200)-Ia* in 3.6%, and *andaph(300)-IIa* 1.2% (Miro' et al. 2013). Underscoring the association of AMEs with resistance elements to other key antibiotic classes, many of these isolates also produced ESBLs and were resistant to the fluoroquinolones. Similar to the AMEs, comprehensive data describing the prevalence and molecular epidemiology of RMTs is lacking. A recent literature review described reports of widespread, global dissemination of genes encoding RMTs among isolates from both human and livestock sources.

Despite the widespread detection of RMTs across many regions, the prevalence appears to vary by region with the highest rates reported in Asia. A SENTRY surveillance study from the Asia-Pacific region (2007–2008) detected genes encoding RMTs in 6.9% (China), 10.5% (India), 1.5% (Hong Kong), 6.1% (Korea), and 5.0% (Taiwan) of Enterobacteriaceae isolates (Bell et al. 2010). Lower rates (1.3%) of RMTs among Enterobacteriaceae have been reported from single institution or local studies from European medical centers. Similar to the association between AMEs and other key resistance mechanisms, an association between RMTs and specific β -lactamases has been described. Seventy-six percent of the RMT containing isolates described in the SENTRY surveillance study above also possessed a CTX-M ESBL (Bell et al. 2010), and RMTs are frequently found in association with the New Delhi metallo- β -lactamase.⁹

Pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics

Aminoglycosides are poorly absorbed via the gastrointestinal (GI) tract and are, thus, administered via the intravenous or intramuscular route. The volume of distribution for members of the aminoglycoside class approaches total body volume, indicating a broad distribution into tissues, including the lung. This feature has led to extensive use of aminoglycosides as part of combination regimens for the treatment of pneumonia. Aminoglycosides are rapidly cleared through the urinary tract, which also makes these drugs ideal for the treatment of urinary tract infections. The relationship between aminoglycoside pharmacokinetics (PKs) and pharmacodynamics (PDs) has been studied extensively in mice. The PK/PD variable that is most often correlated with efficacy of aminoglycosides is the ratio of area under the concentration–time curve (AUC) to MIC, although peak concentration also appears to play a role. The magnitude of the PK/PD target for aminoglycosides is not as well defined as it is for other antibiotic classes because of, until recently, the lack of development of new aminoglycosides. Available data suggests that significant variations

in the PK/ PD target exist between species and body site of infection. For example, an AUC/MIC target of 100 was reportedly associated with a 1- to 2- log₁₀ kill in the mouse neutropenic thigh infection model with amikacin and *K. pneumonia*, whereas this same group reported better efficacy at the same dose level and with the same strain in the mouse lung infection model. These results were potentially a result of a longer measured PAE in the lung compared with the thigh. AUC/MIC thresholds have been correlated to efficacy in patients in whom extensive PK sampling was also conducted. These case reports and reviews describe a variety of different ways that the AUC/MIC ratio might be used to predict outcomes in patients. Smith *et al.* (2001) reviewed 23 patients with intra-abdominal infections (n = 16) or lower respiratory infections (n = 7) treated with tobramycin infused .30 min to achieve a C_{max} of between 4 and 10 mg/L.¹⁰

A PK/PD model constructed from these patient's data showed that improved efficacy was observed when an AUC/MIC ratio of ≥ 110 was achieved compared with AUC/MIC ratios of < 110 (80% clinical cure rate compared with 47%). Other investigators have found similar correlations between exposure and efficacy. Jacobs (2001) describes the need to achieve an AUC/MIC ratio of 25 for less severe infections or in immune competent patients and a ratio of at least 100 in patients with severe infections and/or those that are immune-compromised. Zelenitsky *et al.* (2003) found significantly improved outcomes in patients with bacteremia treated with gentamicin when AUC/MIC ratios exceeded 70 compared with AUC/MIC ratios < 70 (90% cure vs. 45.5%, respectively). However, a much stronger correlation with outcome was noted for C_{max}/MIC with 84% and 90% clinical cure rates for C_{max}/MIC values of 4.8 or 8 compared with 0% clinical cure for C_{max}/MIC < 2.9 . There is substantial evidence that administering larger doses of aminoglycosides less frequently may be associated with improved outcomes compared with providing the same total daily dose over more frequent dosing schedules. This dosing approach, known as once daily or extended interval dosing, takes advantage of three features of aminoglycosides— concentration-dependent killing, rapid elimination, and a prolonged PAE. Larger doses are thought to increase target body site concentrations to improve PD while minimizing potential toxicity through allowance for a period of time in which there is little or no drug in circulation. The PAE properties of the class allow for an extended period of killing after the drug is cleared from the body and before the next dose is administered. A number of meta analyses of results from clinical trials comparing once versus multiple

daily administration of aminoglycosides have been published. Overall, the results of these studies suggest that once daily dosing is associated with reduced nephrotoxicity and equal, if not slightly improved, efficacy.

Therapeutic drug management (TDM), the clinical practice of measuring drug concentrations at designated intervals for use in optimizing individualized dosage regimens, has further improved the safety profile of aminoglycosides. Older studies using multiple daily doses of these drugs have shown nephrotoxicity rates of 10% to 20% , whereas lower rates of nephrotoxicity ranging from 0% to 14% have been reported with once-daily dosing regimens with dose adjustment guided by the use of TDM. The advantages of once-daily or extended interval dosing of aminoglycosides combined with the use of TDM are now widely accepted and, for many infection types, this dosing approach has become the standard of care.

Clinical uses of aminoglycosides

The spectrum of activity, rapid bactericidal activity, and favorable chemical and pharmacokinetic properties of aminoglycosides make them a clinically useful class of drugs. Aminoglycosides are used as single agents and in combination with other antibiotics in both empirical and definitive therapy for a broad range of indications. In patients with serious infections caused by Gram-negative pathogens, the receipt of empiric combination therapy containing at least one antimicrobial agent to which the pathogen is susceptible leads to lower mortality and improved outcomes. In addition to helping ensure that the pathogen is adequately covered by at least one active drug, the use of empiric aminoglycoside-b-lactam combination therapy has also been theorized to contribute to improved outcomes by taking advantage of the *in vitro* synergy observed between these classes and to prevent the emergence of resistance. Although clinical data to support the latter two theoretical benefits of combination therapy are conflicting, aminoglycosides are often combined with b-lactams for the empirical treatment of severe sepsis and certain nosocomial infections in patients with a high risk of mortality or when there is concern that the causative pathogen may be resistant to more commonly used agents (American Thoracic Society; Infectious Diseases Society of America 2005; More recently, aminoglycosides have increasingly become important components of therapy for patients infected with MDR pathogens, such as carbapenem resistant Enterobacteriaceae (CRE), for whom few treatment options remain. In a retrospective cohort study of 50 cases of sepsis caused by carbapenem- and colistin-resistant *K. pneumoniae*, the receipt of gentamicin as part of

definitive therapy was associated with lower mortality compared with the receipt of non-gentamicin containing regimens (Gonzalez-Padilla et al. 2015). The novel aminoglycoside plazomicin is currently under phase 3 study for the treatment of serious infections caused by CRE. Aminoglycosides are also an important component of combination therapy for multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) and certain non-tuberculous mycobacterial (NTM) infections. Current MDR-TB treatment guidelines recommend inclusion of one of the following agents during the intensive phase of therapy: amikacin, kanamycin, streptomycin, or capreomycin, a cyclic peptide antibiotic that is often considered as an aminoglycoside because of its mechanism of action. Each of these agents possesses potent bactericidal activity against *M. tuberculosis* and the choice of agent depends on previous injectable use (if any) and the likelihood of resistance.^{11,12}

A meta analysis including 32 studies with 9000 treatment episodes did not reveal any clear differences in efficacy among the available agents (World Health Organization 2011). Similar to treatment of MDR-TB, combination therapy for patients with fibrocavitary, severe nodular/bronchiectatic or macrolide-resistant lung disease because of the *M. avium* complex generally includes amikacin or streptomycin (Griffith et al. 2007). Among the rapidly growing mycobacteria, amikacin is the preferred agent for infections because of *M. fortuitum* or *M. abscessus*, whereas tobramycin is the most active agent against *M. chelonae*. Aminoglycosides remain the preferred therapy for certain zoonotic infections such as plague and tularemia. Although streptomycin has traditionally been the agent of choice for these infection types, gentamicin is now widely used because of the broader availability of this agent as well as data suggesting similar efficacy to streptomycin.

CONCLUSION:

The aminoglycosides are a critical component of the current antibacterial arsenal. Their broad spectrum of activity, rapid bactericidal action, and favorable chemical and pharmacokinetic properties make them a clinically useful class of drugs across numerous infection types, including certain protozoal infections. The use of aminoglycosides waned as a result of the emergence of other classes of broad-spectrum agents with improved safety profiles, but the emergence of MDR pathogens has led to renewed interest in this class of drugs. Improved understanding of the drivers of toxicity and efficacy has led to the implementation of optimized dosing regimens that improve safety while maintaining efficacy. Increased understanding of key aminoglycoside resistance

mechanisms combined with innovative medicinal chemistry approaches have led to the synthesis and development of novel agents specifically designed to evade resistance while maintaining potency against fully susceptible isolates.

REFERENCES:

1. Abis GS, Stockmann HB, van Egmond M, Bonjer HJ, Vandenbroucke-Grauls CM, Oosterling SJ. 2013. Selective decontamination of the digestive tract in gastrointestinal surgery: Useful in infection prevention? A systematic review. *J Gastrointest Surg* 17: 2172–2178.
2. Aggen JB, Armstrong ES, Goldblum AA, Dozzo P, Linsell MS, Gliedt MJ, Hildebrandt DJ, Feeney LA, Kubo A, Matias RD, et al. 2010. Synthesis and spectrum of the neoglycoside ACHN-490. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 54: 4636–4642.
3. Aínsa JA, Pérez E, Pelicic V, Berthet FX, Gicquel B, Martínc. 1997. Aminoglycoside 20-N-acetyltransferase genes are universally present in mycobacteria: Characterization of the *aac(20)-Ic* gene from *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and the *aac(20)-Id* gene from *Mycobacterium smegmatis*. *Mol Microbiol* 24: 431–441.
4. Aires JR, Köhler T, Nikaido H, Plešiat P. 1999. Involvement of an active efflux system in the natural resistance of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* to aminoglycosides. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 43: 2624–2628.
5. Almaghrabi R, Clancy CJ, Doi Y, Hao B, Chen L, Shields RK, Press EG, Iovine NM, Townsend BM, Wagener MM, et al. 2014. Carbapenem-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains exhibit diversity in aminoglycoside-modifying enzymes, which exert differing effects on plazomicin and other agents. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 58: 4443–4451.
6. Al Sheikh YA, Marie MA, John J, Krishnappa LG, Dabwab KH. 2014. Prevalence of 16S rRNA methylase genes among β -lactamase-producing Enterobacteriaceae cl
7. Costa Y, Galimand M, Leclercq R, Duval J, Courvalin P. 1993. Characterization of the chromosomal *aac(60)-Ii* gene specific for *Enterococcus faecium*. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 37: 1896–1903.
8. Courvalin P. 1994. Transfer of antibiotic resistance genes between Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 38: 1447–1451.
9. Craig WA. 2011. Optimizing aminoglycoside use. *Crit Care Clin* 27: 107–121
10. Craig WA, Redington J, Ebert SC. 1991. Pharmacodynamics of amikacin in vitro and in mouse thigh and lung infections. *J Antimicrob Chemother* 27: 29–40

11. Culebras E, Marti'nez JL. 1999. Aminoglycoside resistance mediated by the bifunctional enzyme 60-N-aminoglycoside acetyltransferase-200-O-aminoglycoside phosphotransferase. *Front Biosci* 4: D1–D8.
12. Cundliffe E. 1989. How antibiotic-producing organisms avoid suicide. *Annu Rev Microbiol* 43: 207–233.
13. Daneman N, Sarwar S, Fowler RA, Cuthbertson BH, Group SCS. 2013. Effect of selective decontamination on antimicrobial resistance in intensive care units: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Lancet Infect Dis* a. 13: 328–341
14. Gonzalez-Padilla M, Torre-Cisneros J, Rivera-Espinar F, Pontes-Moreno A, Lo'pez-Cerero L, Pascual A, Natera C, Rodri'guez M, Salcedo I, Rodri'guez-Lo'pez F, et al. 2015. Gentamicin therapy for sepsis due to carbapenem-resistant and colistin-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. *J Antimicrob Chemother* 70: 905–913.
15. Griffith DE, Aksamit T, Brown-Elliott BA, Catanzaro A, Daley C, Gordin F, Holland SM, Horsburgh R, Huit G, Iademarco MF, et al. 2007. An official ATS/IDSA statement: Diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of nontuberculous mycobacterial diseases. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 175: 367–416.
16. Hancock RE. 1984. Alterations in outer membrane permeability. *Annu Rev Microbiol* 38: 237–264.
17. Hancock RE, Raffle VJ, Nicas TI. 1981. Involvement of the outer membrane in gentamicin and streptomycin uptake and killing in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 19: 777–785.
18. Hancock RE, Farmer SW, Li ZS, Poole K. 1991. Interaction of aminoglycosides with the outer membranes and purified lipopolysaccharide and OmpF porin of *Escherichia coli*. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 35: 1309–1314.
19. Ho YI, Chan CY, Cheng AF. 1997. In-vitro activities of aminoglycoside-aminocyclitols against mycobacteria. *J Antimicrob Chemother* 40: 27–32.